

PROFILING THE RESIDUAL STRESS IN 6061Al -15% vol. SiC_w COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The residual stress, RS, profiles in a 6061Al-15vol%SiC_w composite and its alloy matrix were determined by synchrotron radiation diffraction, SRD, at the ESRF, Grenoble, France. SRD could resolve the spatial dependence of all three principal components of the RS field. The origin of the macro stress could unambiguously be identified as the parabolic temperature gradient present during quenching and a confirmation of many theoretical works could be given.

KEYWORDS: 6061Al; Micro and Macro-Residual Stress; Synchrotron Radiation, Neutron Diffraction

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites, DRMMCs, such as Al alloys reinforced by SiC, are being increasingly used in structural applications because of their enhanced mechanical properties with respect to the corresponding unreinforced alloy. These properties are strongly dependent on the microstructure and highly influenced by the presence of residual stress, RS, in the material [1].

The RS state of DRMMCs is more complex than that in the unreinforced alloys because of the presence of both macroscopic-RS and microscopic-RS [2]. The macro-RS is caused by all the thermo-mechanical processes that take place during the material fabrication and ulterior heat treatments. RS heavily affects the life in service [3] as it superimpose to applied stress. The micro-RS is due to three main sources [4]: i) the thermal mismatch, ii) the elastic mismatch between matrix and reinforcement, iii) the plastic deformation of the matrix.

In absence of plastic pre-straining and macro-RS, the average microscopic (thermal) RS is compressive in the reinforcement and tensile in the matrix, fulfilling the stress balance on the grain size scale, and therefore on the whole material. The macro-RS distributes along the specimen differently, depending on the geometry of the component and the thermo-mechanical process applied. It has also to balance on the whole sample volume or on any section of it [5]. The distribution of the RS is therefore important to identify failure modes and “hot spots”, where cracks are likely to form. Some theoretical work has been done (see e.g. [6]) to assess the macro-RS spatial distribution in simple cases, and the problem is generally considered already solved in textbooks [7]. As a consequence, only few non-destructive experimental confirmations (mainly by means of neutron diffraction, ND) are available on the RS distribution. For example, Fitzpatrick *et al.* [4] studied the profile around a crack tip of a 2124 Al matrix composite. They reported the distribution of stress along the crack growth direction and its variation with applied load. Dutta *et al.* [8] investigated the variation of the RS as a function of plastic deformation in Al alloy matrix composite bars subjected to four-point-bending tests. They could resolve the typical W profile and found that the micro stress is space-dependent (i.e. it depends on the plastic deformation). This confirmed previous work by Levy-Tubiana *et al.* [9]. However, further experimental confirmations are still needed to validate the theoretical calculations. For example Fitzpatrick *et al.* [10] just *assume* a parabolic profile for the initial state of a 2124Al-17%vol.SiC_p composite. Their data indeed shows some

scatter. This is partly due to the limitations of the spatial resolution achievable with ND. In this sense, the use SRD can yield a great deal of spatially resolved information, in spite of some limitations due to the graininess of the material.

In this work an experiment of SRD has been carried out in order to outline the residual stress profiles on the section of cylindrical samples of 6061Al 15%vol SiC_w composite and unreinforced 6061Al alloy. These profiles have been studied in different material precipitation conditions. It will be shown that indeed the specimen quenching induces a parabolic Macro-RS profile along the samples section, and this profile is essentially present (reduced in magnitude) after successive heat treatments.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The samples used in this study were cylinders (6.5 mm diameter, 13 mm length) of 6061Al alloy and 6061Al-15%vol.SiC_w composite, both produced by powder metallurgy [11]. The composite was labelled E219 and the matrix E220. The cylinders were machined from bars extruded at about 500°C with an extrusion ratio of 27:1, which implies 3.30 true strain. This severe size reduction led to a highly textured matrix material ($\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 001 \rangle$ fibre texture components, with the fibre axis parallel to the extrusion axis) and to some trend of the SiC_w, with an average aspect ratio of about 2, to be aligned with the extrusion axis. Details about the processing route, the texture, and the microstructure of these materials are given in [11,12]. Three precipitation states were measured, T4 or “as-quenched”, T6 or fully hardened condition, and OA or over-annealed.

The T4 condition was obtained after a solution treatment at 520°C for 90 min, followed by quenching in cold water. The T6 condition was achieved by successive annealing at 146°C for 56h for the matrix and for 16h for the composite, as the precipitation kinetics is accelerated by the addition of the reinforcement [12]. The OA condition was achieved by further annealing at 300°C for 100 h.

The residual stress profile along the sample diameter has been studied by means of SRD on the beamline ID31, at the ESRF, Grenoble, France. The beam dimensions chosen were 80 μm height and 500 μm width. The energy was 60 keV, which corresponds to a wavelength $\lambda = 0.207 \text{ \AA}$. The 311 planes for both the Al and the SiC phases were measured. They correspond to $2\theta \sim 9.7^\circ$, and 9.05° , respectively. The resulting gauge volume is a rhomboid prism of $0.08 \times 0.94 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ (short diagonal, long diagonal and width, respectively). The $\sin^2\psi$ method [13] was used, tilting the sample within the scattering plane between $\psi = 0^\circ$ (axial direction) and $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$ (radial or hoop direction). The ψ angle is that between the scattering vector and the extrusion axis. The sample holder was made of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) to minimise beam absorption. The samples were mounted on the sample holder as shows Fig.1. The tilt range available on ID31 was not large enough to cover the whole ψ interval. For this reason, two different setups were used; with the samples mounted vertical and horizontal (see Figs.1.b and c). A cylindrical co-ordinate system (axial, radial and hoop main axes) system has been adopted, in which the principal stress directions coincide with the geometrical ones. In order to obtain the radial and hoop components we have performed measurements along radii in both Z and X directions, see Fig.2. In fact, if the extrusion axis is parallel to the scattering vector \mathbf{q} , the axial strain component is measured. On the other hand, when the extrusion axis is perpendicular to \mathbf{q} , the radial component is measured in a scan along X (X scan), and the hoop in a scan along Z (Z scan), as shown in Fig.2. The hoop and radial strain components were not extracted from the very same point, but rather from two equivalent points located on perpendicular diameters at the same radius. The equivalence of the stress state along a given circumference is valid under the reasonable assumption of a cylindrical symmetry. The pitch of the scans was 0.49 mm in the unreinforced alloy and 0.59 mm in the composite. The minimum distance between the last point and the sample surface was 0.3 mm.

Therefore, we measured 13 points in E220 and 11 in E219, including the sample centre in both cases. The distribution of the measurement points and the orientation of the samples during the measurements of the axial and radial strain components are shown in Fig.2.

Fig 1. a) Photo of the experimental setup on the instrument. The detector lays behind the secondary slit. The rotation table (ω) is on the left b) Vertical mount c) Horizontal mount.

Fig. 2 Scheme of the measurement geometry in the axial and radial/hoop mounts. The components of the stress / strain tensor, depending on the sample position are also indicated.

RESIDUAL STRESS ANALYSIS

To allow a meaningful comparison between composite and unreinforced matrix we will mostly refer to the macroscopic RS, M-RS. In the composite E219, the macro stress σ^M was calculated from the phase-specific total stress $\sigma_{Al/SiC}^T$ by means of the rule of mixtures (ROM), which reads:

$$\sigma^M = (1-f)\sigma_{Al}^T + f\sigma_{SiC}^T \quad (1)$$

where f is the reinforcement volume fraction. Incidentally, the micro stress $\sigma_{Al/SiC}^m$ could then be calculated by means of:

$$\sigma_{Al/SiC}^T = \sigma^M + \sigma_{Al/SiC}^m \quad (2)$$

The total stress corresponds to the measured strains and was therefore simply calculated by means of the Hooke's law [14]. The strain values in all directions were obtained by a linear fit of the ϵ vs. $\sin^2\psi$ plots.

The balance of the axial macro RS component σ_{ax}^M across the sample was used for the determination of d_o [5,15]. In cylindrical geometry, this condition reads:

$$\int_{-R}^R \sigma_{ax}^M \cdot r dr = 0 \quad (3)$$

where R is the sample radius. Since a finite number of measurements has been made, equation (3) can be rewritten as:

$$\sum_i \sigma_{ax,i}^M |r_i| \Delta r = 0 \quad (4)$$

where r_i are the measurement positions and Δr are the gauge volume projections along r . Upon writing the stress in equation (4) as a function of the interplanar spacings d and d_o , one can calculate d_o using the measured values of $d_{(ax,rad,hoop),i}$, r_i , and Δr at each point i . This procedure was used for each material in each condition.

RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the macro-RS components (axial, radial and hoop) along the radius of the composite and the unreinforced matrix samples. The RS states shown correspond to T4, T6, and OA conditions (Fig.3.a,b,c respectively). All the stress components in the T4 and T6 conditions show parabolic profiles (the fitting curves are also shown), although the radial stress looks flatter than the others. In the OA condition the radial and hoop components have a flat distribution, so they were fitted with a simple constant.

The maximum (tensile) stress σ_{max} lies on the sample centre, whereas the minimum (compressive) stress σ_{min} lies at the surface. The axial component shows the largest absolute stress and the largest variations. For any given heat treatment, the axial and hoop stress variations are larger in the alloy than in the composite. Expectedly, the samples have some axial macro deviatoric character due to the sample geometry [14].

Samples in the T4 condition show the largest stress variation along the radius. In T4 the hoop component is larger than the radial, in E220 more than in E219. E219 shows larger error bars than E220, because of the larger scatter of the measurements on the SiC phase. The error of macro-RS was also calculated from the propagation through the ROM.

The parabolic profile flattens considerably after the T6 treatment. The axial stress is essentially the same in the composite E219 and the unreinforced alloy E220. The hoop and radial components differ in the two samples only by a constant.

After the OA treatment the profile of all stress components is almost completely flat and near to zero in the alloy E220: the stress has basically relaxed. The same happens for the composite E219.

However, as remarked above, in all precipitation conditions for E219 and in the over aged E220 there is a constant shift between the axial component profile and both radial and hoop profiles. This rigid translation along the stress axis is around 40 MPa in E219 and 15 MPa in E220 OA. This is most probably due to an instrumental effect, which will be discussed further in this work.

Fig. 3 Macro residual stress profiles as a function of radius in the three different precipitation conditions in the two materials, E219 and E220.

DISCUSSION

Some loose powder samples were measured as reference for both phases. For the Al phase they were treated in the same condition of the bulk samples (T4, T6, OA). A significant difference between the measured (powders) and the calculated (balance condition) values of d_0 was found. Would we use the measured d_0 , this would lead to a shift of all profiles of about

125 MPa (tensile). Consequently, condition (3) would not be satisfied. This difference in d_0 could be attributed to possible different precipitation kinetics in the powder and in the bulk matrix due to the different geometrical constraints in the powders (powder particle size vs. bulk sample size). For this reason, and to comply with stress balance, the theoretical value was preferred.

From a physical point of view it is impossible to have a fully relaxed axial stress while still having a non-zero (and constant) radial and hoop stresses (see Fig.3). Moreover, the total range of variation (see Table 1) of both the radial and hoop stress in the OA conditions is essentially zero. It is therefore reasonable to state that in OA condition, the radial and hoop macro stress should vanish. The observed displacement must then be due to a systematic instrumental error in both materials. Most probably, the use of two different setups has suffered from an energy shift caused by a re-alignment of the monochromator. Since this alignment procedure is automatic, this instrumental error cannot be easily estimated. However, since its effect is a rigid displacement of the profiles the conclusions of this work are not affected by this systematic error.

In order to rule out the effect of the systematic shift of the hoop and radial stress profiles, it is therefore instructive to compare the total range of variation of all macro-RS components (Table 1). This is taken as the stress difference between the centre and the surface of the samples. In fact, the relaxation of the macro-RS is visible in Fig.3, but can be readily quantified from Table 1. Reduction factors from the T4 to the T6 conditions of about 4 for the radial and hoop stress components and about 8 for the axial component can be calculated.

The relaxation factor from the T6 to the OA condition is again of the order 4 for the hoop direction (Table 1), whereas the other two components (Fig.3c) are completely flat and therefore present no variation. Because of this, the deviatoric stress is also slightly parabolic after annealing (with a total range of variation of 15 MPa).

	E219					E220				
	Ax	Rad	Hoop	Hyd	Dev	Ax	Rad	Hoop	Hyd	Dev
T4	146 (10)	92 (15)	146 (15)	128 (14)	18 (18)	195 (2)	81 (2)	204 (2)	160 (2)	35 (4)
T6	42 (10)	36 (20)	18 (15)	33 (16)	9 (22)	53 (2)	17 (2)	26 (2)	32 (2)	21 (4)
OA	4 (10)	0 (20)	0 (15)	1 (16)	4 (22)	18 (2)	0 (2)	0 (2)	6 (2)	14 (4)

Table 1 Macro stress variation (MPa) of the profiles shown in figure 3. $\Delta\sigma = \sigma_{max} - \sigma_{min}$. Errors is in brackets.

It has been mentioned above that the rapid cooling after quenching (to reach the T4 condition) causes a parabolic temperature gradient in the sample [16]. Consequently, all macro stress components show a parabolic behaviour as a function of the radial position (Fig.3). Some further considerations on the RS nature and evolution can be done separating the hydrostatic and axial deviatoric stresses. These stresses read respectively:

$$\sigma_{Hyd} = \frac{\sigma_{Ax} + \sigma_{Rad} + \sigma_{Hoop}}{3} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{Dev} = \sigma_{Ax} - \sigma_{Hyd} \quad (6)$$

Fig.4 shows that both the deviatoric and the hydrostatic stresses have parabolic profiles in the unreinforced alloy E220 for both the T4 and the T6 state. On the other hand, in sample E219 the axial deviatoric component is essentially constant. In the T6 conditions (in both samples) all profiles are sensibly flatter (Figs. 3 and 4). This indicates that the annealing at 146°C partially relaxes the macro RS. This is in disagreement with the results found out in previous works on high strength aluminium alloys [17] and with previous interpretation of neutron

diffraction measurements proposed by the authors [18]. The present results indicate that annealing at just 146°C indeed favours dislocation annihilation and rearrangement.

Fig. 4 Relaxation of M-RS from T4 to T6 a) alloy E220 b) composite E219

In E220 the axial stress dominates since the deviatoric stress profile follows the axial. This result can be explained in the following way: when quenching takes place, plastic flow occurs preferentially along the axial direction simply because of boundary conditions. Along the cylinder axis the dilation/contraction is unconstrained, while it is not in the hoop and radial directions (periodic boundary conditions and small size, respectively). This is confirmed by the profiles of the hydrostatic stress: they are similar to the axial stress profile in each case. On the other hand, in E219 the reinforcement has a damping effect on the plastic flow (of the matrix) and it ‘adds’ local boundary conditions. Therefore the strain along the axial direction is no longer larger than the others and the distribution of the macro-deviatoric RS is basically constant. The fact that the deviatoric stress is almost constant in the composite E219 means that the profiles of all components have the same curvature. This implies that the radial temperature gradient has the same effect on each stress component (the thermal stress is isotropic). In fact, the observed non-zero values (about 30 MPa) can even be attributed to the above-mentioned systematic error and we can conclude that the macro-stress is essentially hydrostatic in both the T4 and the T6 conditions.

In Fig.5 the hydrostatic and deviatoric RS profile relaxation from the T6 to the OA condition is apparent by using a different y-scale. As in Fig.4, both profiles are parabolic in sample E220, but relax significantly after the annealing treatment at 300°C.

The same happens for the composite E219 (Fig.5b). The hydrostatic macro-stress has a range of variation of 30 MPa in T6 and essentially 0 in the OA condition. This suggests an essentially complete relaxation. This conclusion disagrees with ref.[18] and therefore further work is needed to determine the influence of d_0 and of the systematic error found above.

The deviatoric macro stress is flat also in OA, as observed for T4 and T6. Its value is the independent of the heat treatment. This supports the idea that in E219 the macro RS is again essentially hydrostatic due to the constrained plastic flow and that the finite value is only an artefact due to the mentioned systematic error. The fact that the deviatoric stress relaxes with the annealing treatment in the unreinforced alloy and remains constant in the composite is in full agreement with previous investigation carried out by neutron diffraction [18].

Fig. 5 Relaxation of M-RS from T6 to OA a) E220 b) E219

CONCLUSIONS

The Macro-RS distribution within the section of cylindrical samples of a 6061Al 15%vol. SiC_w composite and its unreinforced matrix has been investigated by means of Synchrotron radiation diffraction. The Macro-RS relaxation with different heat treatments has been observed. The following points summarize the results of this study:

- Equilibrium considerations:
Highly spatially resolved measurements along the radius allowed the use of the axial macro stress equilibrium equation within the sample section. From this equation, a theoretical value of the reference lattice parameter d_0 was calculated.
- Separation of phase specific stresses:
From the diffraction data, phase-specific stresses could be determined for the Al and the SiC phase. Using the ROM also a separation of the macro (common to both phases) and the micro (phase specific) stress could be done.
- Macro-RS evolution
The distribution of the three main components of the Macro-RS (axial, radial and hoop) was found to be parabolic, with the sample centre in tension stress and the edges under compression. The following features were detected:

- In the unreinforced alloy, after the T4 treatment the axial component is larger than the other two because of the bigger effect of the temperature gradients: the plastic flow is favoured in the axial direction and limited in the hoop and radial directions, because of geometrical constraints. This effect is not present in the composite, where the reinforcement favours stress re-distribution. In fact, the axial stress is larger in the unreinforced matrix than in the composite. This can also be due to the larger CTE of the former.
- The parabolic profiles flatten with heat treatments: The residual stress present in the T4 condition (as quenched) relaxes significantly after annealing for the T6 condition. Under the assumption of a systematic instrumental error, with further annealing (to the OA condition) the stress seems to relax completely in the composite, but not in the unreinforced alloy, in which some (small) axial stress remains.
- A finite axial deviatoric macro stress is present after the extrusion process. In the unreinforced alloy, this stress is only reduced after the ageing process from T4 to T6, and with further annealing from T6 to OA. On the other hand, it looks to be essentially washed out in the composite E219, where a hydrostatic stress state seems to be present.

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